

HIDDEN CURRICULUM SCALE IN TEACHER EDUCATION: A SCALE DEVELOPMENT STUDYⁱ

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to prepare a valid and reliable measurement tool in order to determine the acquisition of teacher candidates under the hidden curriculum in teacher training process. The research is a field study of descriptive quality. In the development of the scale, firstly the related literature has been examined and a pool of 66 items has been formed. Subsequently, expert opinion was received for scope validity. A draft consisting of 43 items was obtained in the line with the expert opinion. After necessary permissions were obtained, it was applied to Akdeniz University Faculty of Education for the pilot application of the scale. The scale was applied to 259 teacher candidates in the fourth year of study at Akdeniz University Faculty of Education by the researcher on May 6-17, 2019. Factor analysis was performed by using SPSS package program for construct validity of the scale. KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) sampling and Bartlett Sphericity test were applied before factor analysis. As a result, the valid and reliable "Hidden Curriculum Scale in Teacher Education" was developed.

Keywords: hidden curriculum, validity, reliability, teacher education

1. Introduction

Education is the process of training people for specific purposes. In line with these purposes, educational programs are developed to regulate educational practices based

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on the political, economic and social expectations of the society. Educational programs including objectives, content (subject area), learning-teaching activities (educational situations, learning-teaching experiences) and testing situations (assessment) are prepared by the institutions. All schools are obliged to apply the official program. Such programs are called “official curriculum”, “formal curriculum” or “written curriculum”. However, in addition to these programs, students encounter another program which is not written or explicitly mentioned. The elements of this informal program are not clear. Such programs are called “*implicit curriculum*”, “*hidden curriculum*” or “*unwritten curriculum*” (Yüksel, 2004).

Individuals acquire knowledge, skills, attitudes and values through education that begins with the birth and continues throughout life. As a result, behavioral changes occur in individuals. Societies put the responsibility of education on schools in shaping the behaviors of the new generations that will sustain their existence. All the learning experiences that the student has acquired inside and outside the school are included in the education program. Since education theory and policy transformed into practice through education programs, education systems become operational with curriculum (Oral & Yazar, 2017).

Curriculum is also classified according to its aims and functions. According to Posner (1995) curriculum has five different functions (Demirel, 2015, p.4).

- **Official curriculum:** It is the written program which includes the program guide, objectives, lesson plans, the order of processing of the subjects, tools and equipment to be used and evaluation.
- **Operational curriculum:** It is the program that the teacher teaches in the classroom and how they are taught and the students’ learning products.
- **Hidden curriculum:** It is the program not explicitly stated in the official program but affects the students’ lives and includes the norms and values of the society.
- **Neglected curriculum:** It is the program that includes formal or operational programs and includes subjects not taught these programs and the reasons for not being taught.
- **Supporting curriculum:** Apart from the official program, it is the program that supports the learning experiences planned according to the interests and voluntarily basis of the students.

It is stated in the researches about the hidden curriculum that two types of programs are applied in schools. The first type of program is the official program in which the objectives, content, implementation and evaluation activities are clearly stated. The second type of program is the hidden curriculum which is gained by students in the process but not explicitly stated and written. The hidden curriculum involves the acquisition of emotions, attitudes, values, habits and social competences at school (Ercan et al., 2009).

2. Literature Review

The hidden curriculum is a concept that is not been very much aware in education and does not have a common definition. There are different views about when hidden curriculum first appeared, but it was accepted that the concept was first used by Jackson in 1968 in his "Life in Classrooms". According to Jackson (1968), the hidden curriculum is not formal and is not explicitly stated. It has hidden messages that include the norms and values that enable students to adapt to society and prepare them for the future. Students succeed if they comply with these norms and values or they fail if they oppose them.

The hidden curriculum was defined by Yüksel (2004) as "*the knowledge, ideas and practices that emerge during the teaching and learning process other than the objectives and activities specify in the official curriculum and qualifications that the students have achieved. The hidden curriculum that determines the quality of education and training activities covers the school rules, physical and psychological environment and implicit or confidential messages that are given to the students by the administrators and teachers in a hidden way to gain feelings, values, habits and skills.*"

The views of some researches on the hidden curriculum are as follows: According to Gordon (1982), the hidden curriculum is associated with the unplanned acquisition of non-academic qualifications, such as behaviors, trends and social skills in a physical and social environment. According to Lynch (1989), schools have universal and unique hidden features. While the universal ones (such as formal programs, school time and exam procedures) are visible, some of the original ones (social activities, reward system) are hidden. Portelli (1993), on the other hand, emphasizes that by making a logical analysis of the concept of hidden curriculum, the curriculum is made hidden by someone else or that the curriculum is implicitly unconscious. Mariani (1999) states that the curriculum is like an 'ice berg' and that the visible part of the iceberg, which is above the water, consists of "*objectives, subjects, time arrangements, methods, etc.,*" whereas the invisible part of the iceberg consists of "*beliefs, attitudes and expectations of teachers, students, families and administrators*". The underwater program is largely unknown, not discussed and often overlooked. In addition, there are beliefs and attitudes in the bottom layer of the curriculum (iceberg), individual styles, intelligence and abilities in the second layer, learning process in the third layer, strategies in the fourth layer and qualifications in the fifth layer above water. According to Tezcan (2005), the hidden curriculum is a learning outcome that is not intended or intended by the school and teacher and where students are not explicitly informed.

In education, the perspectives of individuals in the fields of application implicitly affect the educational process. Detection of the hidden curriculum can only be revealed by long and detailed studies. The hidden curriculum, which is not written but whose existence can be detected indirectly, emerges in educational activities. In fact, students participate in the creation of the hidden curriculum, as the hidden curriculum emerges as it is exposed and reacted to the clearly stated curriculum. This effect of the student on the hidden curriculum is caused by peer interaction and teacher attitudes and

behaviors, which are the most important factors and directiveness of classroom climate. Educators who know this feature of the hidden curriculum should use such a program more consciously and effectively (Bolat, 2014). Hidden curriculum consists of elements such as characteristics of education system and school, architectural structure and decoration of school, determination of classrooms, audiovisual tools used, forms of exams, textbooks, timetables, rules, relations and behaviors of administrators, teachers and students, reward and punishment methods, extracurricular activities, clubs, etc. (Rayn, 1999; Yüksel, 2003). Eisner (1994) investigated why universities such as Prince, Yale and Harvard were superior to other universities and their differences with other universities although their official programs were very similar. She found out that the reason is the way of life in the university and the opportunities offered to them provided by hidden curriculum (Boztaş, 2015; Doğanay & Sarı, 2004; Sarı, 2007; Marsh, 1997; Tezcan, 2003).

After 1950s, Turkey has started to conduct academic studies on program development in a contemporary sense. However, these studies generally focus on formal programs. There is not much research carried out on the hidden curriculum. This may be due to the fact that it is difficult and laborious to conduct research because the hidden curriculum is not clear, specific and written. In this case, since the hidden curriculum was taken into consideration and generally neglected during the education process, the effect of the changes made on official curriculum do not go beyond theory before it could be implemented. Therefore, it is necessary to educate teachers and administrators to reflect this change in textbooks and to make the physical environment suitable for this change by considering the hidden curriculum while developing educational programs (Boztaş, 2015; Sarı, 2007; Taşpolatoğlu, 1993; Tuncel, 2008).

The hidden curriculum is much more effective than formal curriculum in the learning-teaching process. Therefore, it is not enough to develop and change the formal curriculum in order to provide the teacher candidates with required qualifications. In addition, it is necessary to identify faculty of education hidden curriculum and develop it in the line with its objectives. Researches in the field of curriculum in Turkey have been aimed at revealing the learning products obtained as a result of the implementation of official curriculum. Also, the number of studies related to the hidden curriculum is quite low. In the related literature (Başar, 2011; Sarı, 2007; Skelton, 1997; Townsend, 1995; Veznedaroğlu, 2007; Yangın & Dindar, 2010), the hidden curriculum is mostly addressed at primary and secondary level. In recent years, it has been demonstrated by researches (Ahola, 2000; Boztaş, 2015; Tuncel, 2008; Yüksel, 2007) that the hidden curriculum is of great importance for the higher education level. Few studies have been conducted on the hidden curriculum of faculty of education in Turkey (Yüksel, 2003, 2007).

According to Dilci (2012), teaching is a qualification job other than being a profession. Teachers, one of the most important elements of educational institutions, affect the functioning of the system positively or negatively. In order for teachers to have a positive effect on the system, both the theoretical and practical applications of teacher training institutions should be prepared for the teacher candidates in a well-

equipped way. The quality of the teacher is identical to the quality of his/ her education. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the training of teacher candidates in academic and professional terms. Regardless of which level and type of school they are trained, it is essential to gain the teaching qualities in cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects. In the education of teacher candidates, together with the official curriculum, the experiences they have spent in the faculty of education, the teaching staff-student behaviors, the people they interact with, the opportunities provided to the individuals, etc. items play an important role. If the trainees do not have the planned and explicit features in the curriculum, what are the characteristics that trainee teachers should have and how acquire them will be gained through the hidden curriculum (Dilci, 2012; Küçükahmet, 1997).

Teacher training programs aim to develop teacher candidates in terms of field knowledge, general culture and professional aspects. It is thought that the results of the research will contribute to the provision of an effective learning environment, more effective development of teacher training programs and the development of the instructors who play a role in the education of teacher candidates during process of teacher education. Controlling the hidden curriculum by the institution is important in terms of providing the environment for activities that will support the acquisition of positive features. If the hidden curriculum is not controlled by the institution, teacher candidates are likely to encounter negative experiences (Tuncel, 2008).

The fact that theoretical ideas about the hidden curriculum have not been proven by researches leads to questioning the scientific value of these ideas. The reason for this is that the limits of the hidden curriculum concept cannot be determined clearly. It is very difficult to detect it in terms of research methodology. In addition, the lack of a single hidden curriculum in a school and the constant change and development of each hidden curriculum is not seen as another challenge (Gair & Mullins, 2001).

The main function of the faculties of education is to train teachers with the qualifications required by the country. The reason why education faculties failed to gain teacher knowledge, skills and attitudes to teacher candidates was thought to be caused by official curriculum and changes were made through this curriculum. However, the hidden curriculum that emerges in the process and is much more effective than the official curriculum has rarely been considered and discussed. It is necessary to investigate what a hidden curriculum is, what effect it has in the faculties of education, what the teacher candidates have learned in the context of the hidden curriculum and what the instructors teach. In this context, it is important to clarify the hidden curriculum understanding and faculty members in the Faculty of Education (Yüksel, 2007).

3. Material and Methods

The study group consisted of 259 teacher candidates 4th grade students selected by maximum diversity sampling method in the spring term of 2018-2019 academic year at Akdeniz University Faculty of Education. The reason for taking the 4th grade teacher

candidates into the research is that these students have completed all the courses in the faculty of education and have more experience in this faculty. While developing the measurement tool, DeVellis (2017) has taken care of the scale development steps. They are:

- 1) The structure to be measured is clearly defined,
- 2) Item pool is created,
- 3) Measurement format is determined,
- 4) The initial pool of substances is reviewed by experts,
- 5) Valid items are included,
- 6) Items are applied to scale development sample,
- 7) Items are evaluated,
- 8) The scale is optimized.

In the development of the scale, firstly, literature, related measurement and the dimensions of these tools are examined in detail tools (Ahola, 2000; Akbulut & Aslan, 2016; Ercan et al., 2009; Yüksel, 2003). The dimensions to be investigated in the context of the hidden curriculum were determined. In the scale, four dimensions (learning to learn, learning the profession, learning to be an expert, learning the game) determined by Ahola (2000) were taken as the basis. A pool of 66 items was formed. In the context of scope validity, opinions of 7 experts from Curriculum and Instruction Department, 2 experts from Measurement and Evaluation in Education Department and 1 expert from Turkish Language in terms of clarity of items expressions were obtained. Necessary corrections were made according to expert opinion and a draft form consisting of 43 items was obtained. The necessary permission of pilot application of the scale was obtained from Akdeniz University Faculty of Education. The scale was applied to 259 teacher candidates in the 4th grade of Akdeniz University Faculty of Education by the researcher on May 6-17, 2019.

The options and scoring of the likert scale are as follows: "Strongly Disagree-1", "Partially Disagree-2", "Neutral-3", "Partially Agree-4", "Strongly Agree-5". The response time of the scale, which can be applied both individually and in groups, is approximately 15 minutes. For the construct validity of the scale, factor analysis was performed using SPSS program. KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) sample adequacy test and Bartlett Sphericity test were performed before factor analysis. Varimax rotation was used in factor analysis. In determining the number of factors, the criterion of having an eigenvalue greater than 1 was considered. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was examined for scale reliability.

4. Results and Discussion

A. Scale Structure Validity

Factor analysis was performed to scale the construct validity of the scale and factor loadings of the items. According to Bartlett sphericity test ($p < 0.001$) and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO=.913) criterion, it was found to be suitable for factor analysis. In factor analysis, 7 factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 were determined by applying

varimax rotation method. The scree plot graph is given in figure 1. Defined factors and their general variance explanation rates are given in Table 1. The final version of the scale is given Annex 1.

Figure 1: Scree Plot Graph

B. Reliability (Cronbach Alpha Coefficient)

As a result of the analysis, the cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was .948 for the whole scale, .912 for the sub-dimension “Skills for Teaching Practices”, .883 for the sub-dimension “Communication Skill, Being Determined and Systematic”, .815 for the sub-dimension “Learning to Profession”, .830 for the sub-dimension “Scientific Thinking and Discussion Skills”, .805 for the sub-dimension “Learning to Learn”, .799 for the sub-dimension “Skills for Measurement and Evaluation Activities” and .792 for the sub-dimension “Learning to be an expert”. This result shows that the scale is reliable.

Table 1: Factor Analysis Results

Scale Items	Skills for Teaching Practices (F1)	Communication Skills, Being Determined and Systematic (F2)	Learning to Profession (F3)	Scientific Thinking and Discussion Skills (F4)	Learning to Learn (F5)	Skills for Measurement and Evaluation Activities (F6)	Learning to be an Expert (F7)
Item 1: I learned how to establish a good communication with students.	,474						
Item 2: I learned how to establish a good communication with parents of students.	,763						
Item-3: I learned how to inform parents about the development of their children.	,774						
Item 4: I learned to gather information about	,712						

the individual characteristics of students.		
Item 5: I learned how to give homework to students.	,806	
Item 6: I learned how to check the homework of the students.	,857	
Item 7: I learned how to evaluate students' homework.	,855	
Item 8: I learned the importance of building good relationships with the people I will work with.	,512	
Item 9: I learned to be ambitious and determined.	,562	
Item 10: I learned to manage my stress.	,572	
Item 11: I learned to manage my time.	,616	
Item 12: I learned to form a whole order from scattered information sets.	,537	
Item 13: I learned to communicate easily with the instructors.	,584	
Item 14: I learned to communicate easily with my classmates.	,734	
Item 15: I learned that I have to submit my homework on time.	,710	
Item 16: I learned to be responsible for my work.	,658	
Item 17: I learned that effective speaking is as important as having sufficient information on subject in teaching.	,690	
Item 18: I learned the importance of wearing appropriate clothing as a teacher.	,716	
Item 19: I learned that I need to be open to new methods for my professional development.	,785	
Item 20: I learned to express myself correctly.	,513	
Item 21: I learned the importance of the continuity of my self-development in order to be successful in my field.	,551	
Item 22: I learned to think and discuss scientifically.	,756	
Item 23: I learned to use academic language.	,843	
Item 24: I learned evaluate the views and thoughts expressed in the lessons from a scientific point of view.	,671	
Item 25: I learned to study my lessons in planned and organized way.	,831	
Item 26: I learned new study methods.	,713	
Item 27: I learned to be open to learning.	,536	
Item 28: I learned how to use the library and resources.	,537	
Item 29: I learned to adapt to the university grading system.	,814	
Item 30: I learned to adapt to university exam system.	,829	

Item 31: I learned to predict questions that may take in the exam.			,665
Item 32: I learned that I can improve myself professionally by attending scientific meetings (conferences, panels, congresses and workshops, etc.)			,762
Item 33: I learned that I can improve myself professionally by following the literature about my profession.			,680
Item 34: I learned that participating in extracurricular activities (exhibition, meeting, club, community, etc.) is important and useful.			,687
	Total	Variance (%)	Cumulative (%)
Skills for Teaching Practices (F1)	5,070	14,912	14,912
Communication Skills, Being Determined and Systematic (F2)	4,413	12,979	27,891
Learning to Profession (F3)	3,365	9,897	37,788
Scientific Thinking and Discussion Skills (F4)	2,769	8,143	45,931
Learning to Learn (F5)	2,631	7,738	53,669
Skills for Measurement and Evaluation Activities (F6)	2,577	7,580	61,249
Learning to be an Expert (F7)	2,398	7,052	68,302

5. Recommendations

The validity and reliability analysis by different researchers will increase the quality of the prepared scale. Since the hidden curriculum of each faculty of education is different, such research should be carried out by different researchers in different universities. Moreover, similar scale development studies should be conducted to uncover hidden curriculum of different faculties. As these studies become widespread, the hidden curriculum will be taken into consideration in the changes to be made in curriculum.

6. Conclusion

It is known that the changes made on the official curriculum are not reflected on the hidden curriculum. The hidden curriculum needs to be developed in the line with these changes. The opinions of the administrators and faculty members should be taken for the studies to be carried out in the official curriculum and common principles and rules should be determined for in-class and extracurricular activities. Researchers should be encouraged to conduct qualitative and quantitative data collection tools and descriptive and experimental research on the hidden curriculum (Yüksel, 2002a, 2002b).

It is not enough to use only scientific outputs as criteria for success in higher education institutions. In addition to scientific outputs, higher education institutions should be organized according to their educational objectives by examining their own

hidden curriculum. In applications where the hidden curriculum that includes social indicators to satisfy the instructor is not taken into consideration, it is difficult to make real evaluation and the school success of the students is negatively affected. Students behave according to the explicit and hidden expectations of the instructors in order to be successful (Ahola, 2000; Tuncel, 2008; Yüksel, 2004).

This study was conducted in order to develop "Hidden Curriculum Scale in Teacher Education". As a result of the factor analysis, a measurement tool consisting of 34 items and 7 sub-dimensions explaining 68, 302% of the total variance was obtained. The sub-dimensions of the scale are named as: "Skills for Teaching Practices", "Communication Skill, Being Determined and Systematic", "Learning to Profession", "Scientific Thinking and Discussion Skills", "Learning to Learn", "Skills for Measurement and Evaluation Activities" and "Learning to be an Expert". The Cronbach Alpha value is .948 for the whole scale. Consequently, Validity and reliability provided "Hidden Scale Curriculum in Teacher Education" was developed.

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Appendix 1: Final Version of the Scale

Öğretmen Eğitiminde Örtük Program Ölçeği

Sevgili Arkadaşlar,

Bu ölçek, öğretmen yetiştirme sürecinde örtük program kapsamında öğretmen adaylarının edinimlerinin tespit edilmesi amacıyla hazırlanmıştır. Ölçekten toplanacak bilgiler sadece araştırma amacıyla kullanılacaktır. Burada yapacağınız işaretlemeler kesinlikle gizli kalacak ve açıklanmayacaktır. Sizin için en uygun seçeneğin karşısına (X) işareti koyunuz. Lütfen her ifadeyi tek bir işaret koyarak yanıtlayınız. Her maddenin karşısında bulunan; (1) Kesinlikle Katılmıyorum, (2) Kısmen Katılmıyorum, (3) Kararsızım, (4) Kısmen Katılıyorum ve (5) Kesinlikle Katılıyorum anlamına gelmektedir. En uygun yanıtları vermeniz ümidiyle katkınız için teşekkür ederim.

Doktora Öğrencisi
İlknur İzgi İpek

Cinsiyet: 1. Kız () 2. Erkek ()

Bölüm/ Anabilim Dalı:

1. Fen Bilgisi Öğretmenliği ()
2. İlköğretim Matematik Öğretmenliği ()
3. İngilizce Öğretmenliği ()
4. Okul Öncesi Öğretmenliği ()
5. Sınıf Öğretmenliği ()
6. Sosyal Bilgiler Öğretmenliği ()
7. Türkçe Öğretmenliği ()

Baba Eğitim Durumu: 1. Okuryazar değil () 2. İlkokul mezunu ()
3. Ortaokul mezunu () 4. Lise mezunu ()
5. Üniversite mezunu () 6. Lisansüstü eğitim mezunu ()

Baba Mesleği (Lütfen Belirtiniz):

Anne Eğitim Durumu: 1. Okuryazar değil () 2. İlkokul mezunu ()
3. Ortaokul mezunu () 4. Lise mezunu ()
5. Üniversite mezunu () 6. Lisansüstü eğitim mezunu ()

Anne Mesleği (Lütfen Belirtiniz):

Yetiştirdiğiniz Yerleşim Birimi: 1. Köy () 2. Kasaba () 3. İlçe () 4. Şehir ()

Yerleştiğiniz Programın Tercih Sıranız (Lütfen Belirtiniz):

Soru: Bölümünüzde/ Anabilim dalınızda almış olduğunuz eğitimde neler öğrendiniz?

Düzeyi	Katılım					
		Kesinlikle Katılmıyorum (1)	Kısmen Katılmıyorum (2)	Kararsızım (3)	Kısmen Katılıyorum (4)	Kesinlikle Katılıyorum (5)
Maddeler						
Öğrencilerle iyi iletişimin nasıl kurulacağını öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğrenci velileriyle iyi iletişimin nasıl kurulacağını öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğrenci velilerine çocuklarının gelişimi hakkında nasıl bilgi verilmesi gerektiğini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğrencilerin bireysel özellikleri hakkında bilgi toplamayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğrencilere ev ödevlerinin nasıl verilmesi gerektiğini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğrencilerin ev ödevlerinin nasıl kontrol edilmesi gerektiğini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğrencilerin ev ödevlerinin nasıl değerlendirilmesi gerektiğini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Birlikte çalışacağım kişilerle iyi ilişkiler kurmanın önemini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Azimli ve kararlı olmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Stresimi yönetmeyi öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Zamanımı yönetmeyi öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Dağınık bilgi kümelerinden düzenli bir bütün oluşturmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğretim elemanlarıyla rahatça iletişim kurmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Sınıf arkadaşlarımla rahatça iletişim kurmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Ödevlerimi zamanında teslim etmem gerektiğini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Yapacağım işle ilgili sorumluluk sahibi olmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğretmenlikte, konuyla ilgili yeterli bilgiye sahip olmak kadar etkili konuşmanın da önemli olduğunu öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğretmen olarak uygun kıyafet giymenin önemini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Mesleki gelişimim açısından yeni yöntemleri kullanmaya açık olmam gerektiğini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Kendimi doğru ifade etmeyi öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Alanımda başarılı olabilmek için kendimi geliştirmemin devamlılığının önemini öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Bilimsel olarak düşünmeyi ve tartışmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Akademik dili kullanmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Derslerde ifade edilen görüş ve düşünceleri bilimsel açıdan değerlendirmeyi öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Derslerime planlı ve düzenli çalışmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Yeni ders çalışma yöntemleri öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Öğrenmeye açık olmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Kütüphane ve kaynaklardan yararlanma yollarını öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	
Üniversite not sistemine adapte olmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5	

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Üniversite sınav sistemine adapte olmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5
Sınavda çıkabilecek sorularla ilgili tahminde bulunmayı öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5
Bilimsel toplantılara (konferans, panel, kongre, çalıştay vb.) katılarak kendimi mesleki yönden geliştirebileceğimi öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5
Mesleğimle ilgili literatürü takip ederek kendimi mesleki yönden geliştirebileceğimi öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5
Ders dışı faaliyetlere (sergi, toplantı, kulüp, topluluk vb.) katılmanın önemli ve yararlı olduğunu öğrendim.	1	2	3	4	5

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